

USING INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. This scientific article discusses the methodology of effective use of innovative methods in primary education, the importance of didactic games in education, and the role of innovative technologies in classes.

Keywords: didactic games, use of innovative technologies, method, technology, primary education.

INTRODUCTION

Deep and consistent reforms are being carried out in the field of public education, as in all areas of our republic. The main goal of this is to democratize school activities, to develop humanistic principles, to improve the content, form, and efficiency of the educational process. One of the important factors of educating the young generation as a perfect person is to conduct the education and training process based on the requirements of the time, to organize lessons based on the principles of integrity and effectively using innovative pedagogical technologies. Pedagogical technology is the process of influencing students with the help of teaching or education tools by a teacher or educator and forming certain personal qualities in them as a product of this activity.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

It is important to develop students' thinking, consciousness, worldview, and turn them from listeners to participants. The teacher should become the manager of the lesson, and the students should become participants. As long as we, the teachers, can make the students to be free participants in the lessons, we will have

achieved our goal. A teacher should not be limited to teaching the same or similar methods. Do not forget to take into account the age and level of education of more children in primary classes. Starting with simple, easy and time-consuming types, gradually increasing their complexity before conducting didactic games gives a good result. Doing such work, on the one hand, expands children's worldview and consciousness, on the other hand, it strengthens their ability to express themselves, develops creative work skills. It is necessary for the teacher to be able to choose such interactive methods based on the subject and based on a certain goal.

RESULTS

The age and psychological characteristics of primary school students differ sharply in each class. 1st graders are more inclined to play because their attention span is not stable. Therefore, it is necessary to use more didactic games during the lesson.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Computer-based learning in primary grades is seen as changing and enriching the elements of the subject environment. It is at this age that elementary school students undergo a process of rapid development of the child's mental abilities, and a foundation is created for the development of his intellectual potential. The use of pedagogical, innovative and information technologies in the educational process creates an opportunity to effectively solve the current issues of primary education, including:

1. the student's motivation to understand the material increases due to making the educational process interesting and productive;
2. the skills of independent work and self-control develop;
3. ensures the effectiveness of the lesson and the learning of each student;
4. overall optimal development is achieved due to the development of thinking, feeling (chuvstva), aspirations (volya), moral imagination of each

student;

5. active work of all children in the class is ensured.

The application of innovative and information technologies to the educational process can be characterized as a logical and necessary step in the development of the modern information world.

The rapid introduction of computers into the educational process has brought new types and forms of teaching to an unprecedented level in the life of pedagogues. The use of information technologies in primary education is related to solving two main issues: teaching children to use new technical tools and using computer technologies to open and improve new opportunities for students in academic and extracurricular activities. The use of information technology in the classroom has caused great problems for pedagogues. For example, it is necessary for a modern pedagogue to know how to use a computer, to be able to use computer-aided teaching tools and to have the skills to apply them to the educational process, to constantly improve his knowledge of computer-based teaching, and so on.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, if the didactic games given above as an example are conducted in compliance with all the rules and principle requirements, there is no doubt that they will have an effective effect on teaching students to think creatively.

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